

Tectonics

Supporting Information for

Provenance of the Mesozoic succession of Franz Josef Land (north-eastern Barents Sea): Paleogeographic and tectonic implications for the High Arctic

Victoria Ershova^{1,2,3*}, Andrei Prokopiev³, Daniel Stockli⁴, Mikhail Kurapov¹, Natalia Kosteva⁵, Mikhail Rogov², Andrei Khudoley¹, Eugeny O. Petrov⁶

1 St. Petersburg State University, University nab. 7/9, St. Petersburg, 199034, Russia; v.ershova@spbu.ru, 2 Geological Institute of RAS, Pyzhevski lane 7, Moscow, 119017 Russia, 3 Diamond and Precious Metal Geology Institute, Siberian Branch, Russian Academy of Sciences, Lenin av. 39, Yakutsk, 677980, Russia, 4 Jackson School of Geoscience, University of Texas at Austin, Austin, 78712-1692, USA, 5 Polar Marine Geosurvey Expedition, 24, Pobedy st., St. Petersburg – Lomonosov, 198412, Russia, 6 All Russian Geological Institute, Sredniy prospect 39, Saint Petersburg, Russia

Contents of this file

Attachment 8 Results of U-Pb dating of granitic pebble.

sample 18-V15-34/8		Coordinates		81°00.883'		065°21.395'											
Spot	% ²⁰⁶ Pb _c	ppm U	ppm Th	$\frac{^{232}\text{Th}}{^{238}\text{U}}$	ppm ²⁰⁶ Pb*	(1) $\frac{^{206}\text{Pb}}{^{238}\text{U}}$ Age	(1) $\frac{^{207}\text{Pb}}{^{206}\text{Pb}}$ Age	% Dis- cor- dant	(1) $\frac{^{238}\text{U}}{^{206}\text{Pb}^*}$	±%	(1) $\frac{^{207}\text{Pb}^*}{^{206}\text{Pb}^*}$	±%	(1) $\frac{^{207}\text{Pb}^*}{^{235}\text{U}}$	±%	(1) $\frac{^{206}\text{Pb}^*}{^{238}\text{U}}$	±%	err corr
1.1	0.30	448	337	0.78	32.4	518.7±3.5	522±62	1	11.934	0.7	0.0578	2.8	0.668	2.9	0.08378	0.7	.239
2.1	0.08	1075	502	0.48	77.5	518.8±2.7	511±30	-2	11.931	0.54	0.0575	1.4	0.6644	1.5	0.08381	0.54	.362
3.1	0.26	901	978	1.12	66.1	527.1±2.9	450±46	-15	11.735	0.57	0.0559	2.1	0.657	2.2	0.0852	0.57	.262
4.1	2.07	670	225	0.35	49.2	517.3±3.6	708±110	37	11.957	0.72	0.063	5.2	0.726	5.2	0.08355	0.72	.139
5.1	--	266	132	0.51	19.1	517.9±4.4	560±88	8	11.95	0.89	0.0588	4	0.678	4.1	0.08366	0.89	.215
6.1	0.29	634	468	0.76	45.9	520.6±3.2	493±58	-5	11.887	0.64	0.057	2.6	0.662	2.7	0.08411	0.64	.234
9.1	0.49	215	87	0.42	15.8	527.4±5.1	675±120	28	11.73	1	0.062	5.8	0.729	5.9	0.08526	1	.171
10.1	0.42	301	96	0.33	21.5	512.8±4	473±86	-8	12.074	0.82	0.0565	3.9	0.645	4	0.0828	0.82	.206
7.1	0.78	778	6	0.01	77.6	702.3±4	612±60	-13	8.684	0.6	0.0602	2.8	0.956	2.8	0.1151	0.6	.212
8.1	6.25	988	935	0.98	69.7	476.8±4.2	1459±110	206	12.99	0.92	0.0915	5.9	0.969	5.9	0.07677	0.92	.156

Errors are 1-sigma; Pbc and Pb* indicate the common and radiogenic portions, respectively.

Error in Standard calibration was 0.31%(not included in above errors but required when comparing data from different mounts).

(1) Common Pb corrected using measured 204Pb.